

DON QUIXOTE'S EXPRESSION IN JOSEPH CONRAD'S *THE HEART OF DARKNESS AND NOSTROMO*

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Abstract:

Cervantes wrote "Don Quixote". Don Quixote was noted for his adventurous and chivalric deeds. Quixotic experience is a must in today's competitive world. The aim of this paper is to create awareness about quixotic experience in a person's life. In this modern era, most of the persons lead a very ordinary life. They have no inclination to take any risks. The greatest risk in one's life is not taking any risk at all. Taking risk is quite inevitable. No one is exempted from risk-free life. Every profession has a considerable and noteworthy risk. In the world of cricket, most of the players take calculated risks in batting, fielding, etc. In the world of vast sea, one can anticipate unexpected risk in one's life. Joseph Conrad was a sea dog. He had a vast experience in the world of sea. He reflected his authorial voice in most of his novels. He was teeming with quixotic experience. Quixotic experience makes the life of any man sprightly. It makes body and soul intact. He was really adept in exploring the unknown mysteries of the sea. In his "Heart of Darkness", the narrator of the novel Marlow expressed his quixotic experience in a very crystal-clear manner. His experience in sea is a fruitful lesson to all the readers. Some of the readers of Joseph Conrad's novels derive a divine inspiration from his characters. Nostromo was an Italian sea dog. He established himself as a prominent leader. In the vast sea, he expected the unexpected. He possessed bravery, team spirit, quixotic nature. He learnt certain things in the vast ocean. At last he was killed by a person out of mistaken identity. But he had quixotic experience. The aim of this paper is to bring out this experience to the readers. One must possess an adventurous spirit to drink life to the lees. Ulysses, a man of adventure, drank life to the lees. Like him, Nostromo and Marlow derived a lot of adventurous spirit in the vast sea.

Key words:

Quixotic experience, sea dog, coverage, adventures rippling, lively, bestial romantic imagination, river, waterway and enraptured Thrill.

Don Quixote was a remarkable character. He was an evergreen character. Cervantes delineated the character of Don Quixote. His life is full of chivalry and adventures. He is a rippling sort. He has a universal appeal. His attitude is crystal clear. He wanted to drink life to the lees like Ulysses; he had an inherent desire for adventures. Joseph Conrad was a sea dog. He was a prolific writer. He had a vast experience in the vast sea. His life was filled with adventures and sprightly action. He wanted to become a fresh water sailor. He hailed from Poland. He happened to meet different types of people. He had an indomitable spirit. He viewed life as a voyage.

In 1874, at the age of seventeen, Conrad wanted to become a sailor. Conrad was not at all idle. He hated idleness. He wanted to lead meaningful life in the vast sea. In the beginning, he knew nothing about the sea. But he never felt jittery. He wanted to face life boldly like Don Quixote. Cervantes shaped the character of Quixote. Like that, Joseph Conrad's uncle shaped the life of Conrad. Conrad needed freedom at any cost. His country Poland never provided him freedom. He suffered from illness. He was smitten by Malaria. But Joseph Conrad had nerves of iron. He reached Congo. He made several voyages to far Eastern waters. He never felt jetlag.

The Heart of Darkness is an impression taken from life. Marlow was an important character in the novel "The Heart of Darkness". Marlow wanted to become a fresh water sailor. He had a spirit of adventures. Conrad encountered a lot of unexpected experience only in the vast sea. His health was affected. He had some physical infirmities. He was very weak in health condition. But he had a strong will to face life boldly. He created a lively character named Marlow. He expressed his personal experience through Marlow.

Conrad created another character named Nostromo. Nostromo was an Italian sailor. Nostromo has romantic imagination. At the same time, he has a spirit of adventure. To his attitude the work now allotted to him will be the most famous and dangerous adventure of his life. His boat is nearly wrecked in the night by the steamer by the steamer bringing the attacking soldiers. He succeeds in reaching to the land and burying the treasure. When he returns, the rebels are in procession. He finds himself in an awkward situation. He has no money in his hands. He has a lot of grit to face the unexpected events boldly. He makes the spectacular dash from the town on an engine up the mountain over the mountain on horseback to capital and returns with the soldier by sea in time to save the day. Nostromo visits his treasure island at night. He carries away the treasure of silver. His life is teeming with adventures. He never reckons his condition of penury. Nostromo loves Giselle. Giselle is the youngest daughter of Viola. Nostromo hopes to run away with Giselle. He cannot resist coming to the light- house at night to see his sweetheart. He suffers from love bug. But Viola kills him by mistake.

Conrad himself used some appropriate words to describe the bold sprit of Nostromo

"The impious adventures gave no other sign" (Nostromo p. 18)

Joseph Conrad was a real cat whisker in describing the eerie atmosphere of the sea. He became weak. But his will power became strong. He never gave up his spirit of adventures due to his physical infirmities. He described the atmosphere in a very clear cut manner.

“At night the body of clouds advancing higher up the sky smother the whole quiet gulf below with an impenetrable darkness, in which the sound of the falling showers can be heard beginning and ceasing abruptly.” (Nostromo p. 20)

But Nostromo had no fear. His life is full of adventures. He has Quixotic Spirit. He wanted to proceed further without having any rumination. Nostromo was a sea dog. He can tackle any bottleneck moment single handedly.

Charles Gould praised the capabilities of Nostromo to a great extent. He felt astonished to see the boldness of the Italian sailor Nostromo. He declared

“This young fellow”, he thought to himself, may yet become a power of the land”. (Nostromo p.77)

Nostromo had no other second thoughts. He accepted the task. He never gave room for brown study. He wanted to hide the silver ingots in a secret place. He wanted to do an act of adventure single handedly. He needed no moral support. He needed no companions. He wanted to face any danger with indomitable spirit. Like Ulysses, he wanted to lead meaningful life. He hated pot boil existence. Nostromo was competent enough for his special task in the plan of campaign. Nostromo believed in miracles. He heard a lot of tales from his kith and kin. He wanted to accomplish this special task in a very successful manner.

“Nostromo made a superhuman effort” (Nostromo p. 434)

Nostromo was a very courageous man. He accomplished his task very successfully. He faced a lot of teething troubles in the form of attacking soldiers. But he tackled everything with a sense of grit and fierce determination.

Captain Mitchell made possible comments on Nostromo. Nostromo was very assiduous. He discharged his duties very earnestly. He was a platonic lover. He endangered his life out of earnest love. But he was filled by a woman. She misconceived him as an intruder.

“The fellow is devoted to me, body and soul” Captain Mitchell was given to affirm” (Nostromo p. 49)

As an Italian sailor, he never did any work in a very slipshod manner. He was not a man of hedonism. He viewed life with a lot of sensibility. He became a sailor out of enthusiasm. He viewed the entire world as vast sea. It gave him a sense of solace. It gave a sense of thrill. The vast sea gave him a lot of happiness. He was imported to work upon the National Central Railway. Nostromo became the terror of all the thieves in the town.

“It could very well be said that it was Nostromo alone who saved the lives of these gentlemen” (Nostromo p. 25)

Nostromo was a man of action. He was not at all a coward. He wanted to take a lot of risks. As a worker, he was spotless. As a lover he was very earnest. Joseph Conrad delineated the character of Nostromo to a great extent. His spirits seemed to be quixotic. His experience was basically quixotic. He loved adventures. He loved Voyages. He visited different countries. He discerned a sense of danger in front of him. But he approached life in a very positive manner. There was no room for complacency. He wanted to drink life to the lees. The vast sea made him very courageous. He died abruptly. But he had a sense of complacency.

Marlow was the narrator of the shorter novel The Heart of Darkness. Marlow was basically quixotic. He too loved adventures. He was a kind as well as courageous person. He took bold decisions. He never felt perplexed. He wanted to become a fresh water sailor. He wanted to visit different places. He hated idleness. Marlow was a sea dog. Joseph Conrad expressed his personal experiences in the form of Marlow. His life on land seemed to be very monotonous. But his life on the vast sea seemed to be quite enterprising.

He described the sea with much poetic sensibility. He says

“The Sea – reach of the Thames stretched before us like the beginning of an interminable waterway. In the offing the sea and the sky were wedded together without a joint”. (The Heart of Darkness pg., 1)

Marlow felt enraptured to describe sea. He had sense of thrill while voyaging. He happened to meet different types of persons. So his life was not at all monotonous. It was like an interesting enterprise. As a perfect raconteur, he narrated some interesting events to his fellow sailors. His life was full of action packed events. He did not want to remain idle. He wanted to live the life with adventures. He had an indomitable spirit. He relished voyages a lot. Marlow had a primary inspiration. As a perfect historian, he narrated the activities of the Romans. They were basically courageous. Marlowe says

“They were men enough to face the darkness” (The Heart of Darkness p. 9)

He described about the courageous nature of the Romans. Marlow was greatly inspired by the attitude of the Romans. The Romans had a spirit of adventures. They led a sprightly life. Like them, Marlow too wanted to lead a sprightly life. He became the fresh water sailor. He gained a lot of experience in the form of voyages

“It was upward of thirty days before I saw the mouth of the big river we anchored off the seat of the government. But my work would not begin till some two hundred miles farther on. So as soon I could I made a start for a place thirty miles higher up”. (The Heart of Darkness p. 21)

He was really fascinated by the river. He put his heart and soul to relish the vastness of the sea as well as the river. As a fresh water sailor, he relished his life to a great extent. He had a noble vision. He was the friend of Mr. Kurtz. He wanted to carry actually Mr. Kurtz from that place. In the form of voyage he had some blissful experience. But he felt perplexed to watch the activities of the African people. They behaved in a very bestial manner.

The aim of this paper is to create awareness in the minds of modern men and modern women. Modern men lead a very happy and carefree life. They do not have any noble aim. They indulge in pot boil existence. Don Quixote was noted for his noble action. Nostromo was noted for his spirit of adventures. Marlow was a bit nosy type. Through these characters, one can come to the conclusion that. One should lead life which is full of enterprising events. According to C.Rajagopalachari, *“Idleness is the worst enemy”*. So this paper is a fruitful lesson to all the modern man and the woman. Existing is meaningless. Living is meaningful. So through the characters of Don Quixote, Ulysses, Nostromo and Marlow. The reader can learn a fruitful lesson.

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